

"THE DEVELOPMENT OF MILITARY ART DURING THE TIME OF AMIR TEMUR AND THE TIMURIDS AND ITS SIGNIFICANCE TODAY"

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Annotation: The great statesman Sohibkiron Amir Temur, who left his name in the annals of history of our homeland, took a worthy place in world history with his sharp intellect, unique leadership skills and military skill. The life path of the commander and the success he achieved during his state administration and activities are reflected in a number of historical works.

Keywords: The need for scientific study of theoretical issues related to the personality, spirituality, and morality of Amir Temur is associated with the analysis of his moral principles that determine the development of the people, state, and society. Justice played an important role in the activities of Sahibkiran Amir Temur.

In particular, the national and universal significance of the "Temur Regulations" is determined by the fact that they are based on high moral principles, which is precisely due to Sahibkiran's attitude to justice. Justice was interpreted as a moral criterion of Amir Temur's activities.

For today's generation, there are many moral qualities in the personality of Amir Temur, such as honesty, courage, foresight, perseverance, determination, which are of great benefit and wisdom to study and practice. Accordingly, Sahibkiran's moral essence of military patriotism:

-that the figure of Amir Temur is a spiritual courage in raising a person who is determined, courageous, responsible and has a civic position;

-that the exemplary life and work of Amir Temur in the "Temur Regulations" is a pragmatic basis for strengthening the independence of the Motherland;

-that sources in our country and abroad that interpret Amir Temur as the "great savior of the Motherland" have been studied;

-that the sahibkiran can be characterized by moral qualities such as being cultured, broad-minded, well-versed in art and literature, a patriot and a person who loves his people.

It is worth noting that, combining the information provided on the study of Amir Temur's activities, we believe that it is important for today's defender of the Fatherland to form such military-patriotic qualities as determination, courage, responsibility in fulfilling each assigned task, loyalty in fulfilling civic duty, love and loyalty to the country, and tolerance.